

Promotional events as an effective strategy to elicit blood donations: an evaluation of cost and benefit

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ABSTRACT

Background: The availability of blood and blood products is crucial for the provision of high quality hospital services. Successful donor recruitment and retention campaigns including pro-motional events are common strategies to help attract blood donations and donors. However, such events can be costly and must be considered in light of alternative interventions. We aimed to evaluate the effect of 1-day events on a) total blood donations b) donor recruitment (first-time donations) and c) donor retention (repeat donations) over multiple years in a public hospital setting. In addition, we estimated the cost per additional unit of blood gained from the perspective of the blood donation centre.

Methods: We utilise administrative data from the Universitätsklinikum Hamburg-Eppendorf (UKE), a hospital with 1,460 beds and a substantial share in the blood donation market in Ham-burg (1.8 million inhabitants) and data from a second Hamburg based blood donation centre (Albertinen House). We conduct a difference-in-differences (DiD) analysis to identify causal effects of the hospital-based “Bikers Blood for Help” (BBFH) days, a biker themed open-air event with live music in collaboration with local motorcycle enthusiasts aimed at promoting blood donation, that took place at the UKE in 2015, 2016 and 2017. We use data from another blood collection site unaffected by the event as a control group for our evaluation and analyse the number of total, first time and repeat donations. In addition, we consider the cost of the event including the staff involved and the disposable costs consumed during the event to estimate the cost per additional unit of blood gained.

Results: Preliminary estimates suggest that the “Biker for Blood” events had a positive effect on total, first-time and repeat donations increasing them over a 3-month period on average by 231, 143, and 88, respectively. In addition, although we find that the event was most effective in 2017 increasing donations by 379, the result was not statistically significant (p value: 0.870). The cost of the event from the centre perspective ranged between €7,465 and €8,427 with an additional €5,280 spent on staff costs. Preliminary results suggest that the cost per additional unit of blood from the event ranged from €133 – €144 which exceeds the cost of collecting blood during regular hours.

Conclusion: The preliminary results suggest that 1-day promotional events are an effective tool for eliciting blood donations but may not be cost effective over short periods. Further research to consider the long-term effects of the events is still required as well the wider benefits of the event to the centre in terms of the increased public awareness and organisational reputation gained through community engagement.